

INFLUENCE OF AIR RELEASE ADDITIVE ON VACUUM-BAG CURABLE PREPREG

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Abstract

The principles of air bubbles in the resin removed by air release additive were analyzed, and the influence of air release additive BYK®-A 560 on the properties of vacuum bag cure T700/VB-90 composite had been investigated here. The main physical properties and mechanical properties of the BYK®-A 560 incorporated T700/VB-90 prepreg were evaluated, and the results were compared to those from original T700/VB-90 prepreg without BYK®-A 560. The quality of T700/VB-90 composite laminates was improved significantly by incorporating BYK®-A 560. Results of optical microscopy, ultrasonic C-Scan, void volume content and mechanical test have shown that the laminates from BYK®-A 560 incorporated T700/VB-90 prepreg had autoclave cure quality with excellent mechanical properties. Hot/wet test results indicated that the incorporation of BYK®-A 560 had no negative influence on the main mechanical properties and heat resistance of T700/VB-90 composite which could be serviced as high as 90°C as a structure material. A novel vacuum bag cure only prepreg with promising characteristics is being developed.

Keywords: vacuum bag cure; prepreg; epoxy; carbon fiber; carbon fiber composite

1. Introduction

The main advantages of advanced composites are their high performance and low density. The high cost of advanced composite parts is the key limit for their extensive utilization in aerospace industry, weapon system and naval vessel field.

In the last ten to fifteen year as an industry we have worked at alternative manufacturing methods to reduce the cost of a given quality of composite structure. One aspect of this overall effort has been to develop composite materials that can be processed to a high quality without use of an autoclave [1-3]. An autoclave is a heated pressure vessel used extensively in the aerospace industry for the manufacture of composite parts. Many smaller composite companies would like the quality of part routinely produced by autoclave processing but cannot justify the expenditure that installing an autoclave would entail. Autoclave are also subjected to the “Garage Volume Law”-However large your garage your junk increases to fill the available space [1]. Composite structures are getting larger and finding an autoclave of correct size can be a major logistical problem that makes the design and production engineer look to alternative methods of manufacture. One potential solution to these problems would be a hypothetical composite material as strong, as stiff and as cosmetically perfect as an autoclave part but requiring only low pressure and low temperatures to achieve the desired results [4,5].

Advances in our understanding of processing of composite materials and improvements in formulations and formatting of prepreps have resulted in major improvements in the molded quality of oven heated, vacuum only consolidated laminates.

The initiative of reducing cost leads authors of this paper to develop vacuum bag cure only technique to manufacture advanced composite with high performance. VB-90 is an epoxy resin matrix with excellent mechanical properties and outstanding processability developed by the authors here. Even though the mechanical properties of the composite are high, however, there

were always some small voids can be found in the composite laminates when they were manufactured with vacuum bag cure only technique. One kind of air release agent was incorporated into the VB-90 resin to remove the voids in the VB-90/T700 composites after analyzing the characteristics of the voids in the composite. The quality and properties of the air release agent incorporated composite have been investigated, and significant results have been achieved.

2. Experimental section

2.1. Raw Materials

Air release additive BYK®-A 560, solution of foam destroying polyacrylates and polymers, BYK-Chemie GmbH. VB-90 resins and prepreg with T700 as the reinforcing fiber are developed by Beijing Institute of Aeronautical Materials (BIAM). 1% BYK®-A 560 (based on pure VB-90 resin) was incorporated before the curing agent was mixed with the epoxies during the preparing process of VB-90 resin.

2.2. Preparation of T700/VB-90 Prepreg

The T700/VB-90 prepreg was prepared by a hot/melt technique using a prepregger made in USA. The resin film was prepared at $55\pm 5^{\circ}\text{C}$, the initial impregnation temperature was $75^{\circ}\text{C}\sim 95^{\circ}\text{C}$, the pressures of the front, middle and rear pressing rollers were 0.1MPa, 0.2MPa and 0.3MPa, respectively, and the producing speed limit was $1\sim 2\text{m}/\text{min}$.

2.3. Standard Manufacturing Parameters of T700/VB-90 Laminates

All the T700/VB-90 laminates were manufactured with vacuum bag cure only process in a heated air oven. The manufacturing thermal cycle is : $70^{\circ}\text{C}/1\text{h}+130^{\circ}\text{C}/2\text{h}$.

2.4. Characterization and Determination

The glass transition temperature (T_g) of composite was evaluated by dynamic mechanical thermal analysis (DMTA), the heating rate was $5^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$ and the frequency chosen was 1Hz. T_g was reported as the peak in $\tan\delta$. Ultrasonic C-scanning detection of laminates was performed on a home-made apparatus with the same condition as the laminates manufactured by an autoclave, the frequency selected was 5MHz. All the mechanical properties of laminates were tested according to Chinese Standards using a 10T Instron machine, see Table 1. Micrographic inspections were performed to examine the coupons for voids. Microsections were prepared by placing a piece machined from the laminates, approximately 20mm by 20mm, into a sample holder and mounting it with epoxy. The specimens were then ground and polished using typical metallographic procedures and then examined using an optical microscope at 20x and 40x. When voids were observed, a photograph was taken.

Table 1
Test standards for T700/VB-90 laminates

Tests	Standards
Tensile test	GB/T 3354
Flexural test	GB/T 3356

Compression test	GB/T 3856
Short beam shear test	GB/T 3357

Table 2
Main properties of T700/VB-90 prepreg

Parameters	Values
Content of volatile (%)	<1.0
Content of resin (%)	36±3
Stickiness	Eligibility
Percent of resin flow (%)	10~25
Storage life at RT (day)	>60
Thickness of single ply(mm)	0.125±0.01

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Analyses of mechanism of air bubbles removed by air release additive

Why air release agent is selected and incorporated in the resin system here? First we should know the voids characteristics in the vacuum bag cure only laminates. The unidirectional and symmetric lay-up composites manufactured from T700/VB-90 prepreg by using vacuum bag cure only technique are cut and polished to observe the voids in the composites. As shown in Fig. 1, the voids in both kinds of laminates are very small, and most of them are less than 1mm in diameter. On the other hand, all the voids are distributed in the resin between two adjacent fiber layers.

Fig.1. Optical photographs from VB-90/T700 laminates

Then, we analyzed how the voids are formed in the laminates. Most of the voids were caused by entrapped air and volatiles (include absorbed water) in the prepreg [1]. Both the entrapped air and volatile should be released before the gelling point of resin reached. As we mentioned above, all the voids are very small and exist between the adjacent layers, and it is difficult to remove those small voids. This reminds us of the air release additive. The main working principles for an effective air release additive should include: (1) have a low surface tension than that of the resin to be deaerated; (2) have a positive spreading coefficient which produces an positive bubble coalescence effect; (3) be insoluble in the medium to be

deaerated. An air bubble is usually stabilized by the interfacial active substances between the bubble and surrounded resin; the air release additive molecules will take the place of these interfacial active substances if an air release additive is incorporated, so the surface tension of the resin will be decreased significantly, and the bubbles will go through the fiber layer more easily than before. On the other hand, the void bubbles will coalesce to become big and the number will be reduced. According to Stoke's Law,

$$v \propto \frac{r^2}{\eta}$$

Where v is the speed movement of air bubble, r^2 is the square of the radius of the bubble, and η is the viscosity of the resin. Because the viscosity of the air release additive (usually contains solvent) is very low, so the viscosity of the resin will be reduced significantly when an air release additive is incorporated, and the air bubbles in the resin pool will move faster than those without the addition of air release additive.

So if the solvent in the air release additive can be removed before the gelling point of resin is reached, the air trapped can escape from the resin simultaneously during the manufacturing process.

3.2. Influence of air release additive on the quality of T700/VB-90 laminates

Air release additive BYK®-A 560 (BYK-Chemie GmbH), solution of foam destroying polyacrylates and polymers, was selected here to verify the theory of above analyses. Fig.2 shows typical micrographs of laminates manufactured from T700/VB-90 prepreg with the incorporation of BYK®-A 560. Voids were only found in the laminates from original T700/VB-90 (Fig.1), no voids can be seen in these photographs corresponding to BYK®-A 560 incorporated system. In order to verify the quality of laminates by incorporating BYK®-A 560, ultrasonic inspections were performed to check the quality of composite laminates. As shown in Fig.3, the ultrasonic C-Scanning pictures of BYK®-A 560 incorporated laminates are much better than those without BYK®-A 560. Both the results of the optical photographs and ultrasonic inspection have indicated that the quality of composite laminates had been improved significantly by incorporating air release additive BYK®-A 560, and composite laminates with autoclave cure quality have been manufactured successfully by using vacuum bag cure only technique.

(1) Laminate $[-45/0/-45/90]_{4S}$

(2) Laminate $[0]_{16}$

Fig.2. Optical micrographs of BYK®-A 560 incorporated T700/VB-90 laminates

(1) Laminate $[0]_{16}$ without BYK®-A 560

(2) Laminates $[0]_{16}$ with BYK®-A 560

(3) Laminate $[-45/0/-45/90]_{4S}$ without BYK®-A 560

(4) Laminate $[-45/0/-45/90]_{4S}$ with BYK®-A 560

Fig. 3. Ultrasonic C-scanning pictures of T700/VB-90 laminates

3.3 Main properties of T700/VB-90 composites

In order to check out the influence of BYK®-A 560 on the properties of T700/VB-90 composites, main mechanical properties and hot/wet properties of T700/VB-90 laminates had been determined. As shown in Table 3, there is no significant differences between the

properties of laminates with and without BYK®-A 560, but a slight improvement of BYK®-A 560 incorporated T700/VB-90 composites can be seen in Table 3 because of the reduced voids in those laminates. As shown in Table 3, the vacuum bag cure laminates has just a very slightly higher void content than the autoclave cured laminates. Mechanical property testing has shown comparable results of BYK®-A 560 incorporated T700/VB-90 laminates fabricated by vacuum bag cure to those laminates fabricated from autoclave.

Table 4 gives the hot/wet properties of T700/VB-90 laminates with and without BYK®-A 560. Results have indicated that the incorporation of BYK®-A 560 does not change the heat resistance of T700/VB-90 composite. Two of the main reasons are that the content of air release additive is very low (1% based resin weight) and the high percentage solvent in BYK®-A 560 should have been removed before the gelling point of the resin. Hot/wet properties indicate that the service temperature of T700/VB-90 composite can reach 90°C.

From above results, we can deduce that vacuum bag cure only technique can produce T700/VB-90 laminates with low void contents (about 1%), high fiber volume (60%) and excellent mechanical properties (shown in Table 3), and these properties approach those typically expected of autoclave cured prepreg materials.

Table 3

Main mechanical properties of T700/VB-90 composite at room temperature

Parameters	With BYK®-A 560 <i>Vacuum bag cure</i>	Without BYK®-A 560 <i>Vacuum bag cure</i>	With BYK®-A 560 <i>Autoclave cure</i>
0° Tensile strength (MPa)	2301	2093	2356
0° Tensile modulus (GPa)	127	128	128
Flexural strength (MPa)	1501	1497	1499
Flexural modulus (GPa)	116	116	116
0° Compressive strength (MPa)	1220	1080	1208
Short beam shear strength (MPa)	76.5	74.5	77.0
Void volume content,%	3.2	1.1	0.3

All data represent the average of 5 replicates; data are not normalized and based on actual thickness, and fiber volume content in all tested laminates is 60-64%; 0.4MPa was applied during the autoclave cured process; void volume content was determined using ASTM D3171 testing method.

Table 4

Hot/wet properties of T700/VB-90 composite

Parameters	Test conditions	With BYK®-A 560	Without BYK®-A 560
Flexural strength (MPa)	RT (dry)	1501	1497
	90°C (dry)	1241	1262
	90°C (wet)	1081	1062
Flexural modulus (GPa)	RT (dry)	116	116
	90°C (dry)	119	119
	90°C (wet)	120	117
Short beam shear strength (MPa)	RT (dry)	76.5	74.5
	90°C (dry)	55.6	54.0
	90°C (wet)	42.8	41.0
Tg (°C)	(dry)	162	162

Note: the wet coupons were immersed in 95°C-100°C distilled water for 48h.

4. Conclusion

Analyses of the principles of air release additive removing air bubbles in the resin have indicated the void volume contents in advanced composite can be reduced by incorporating air release additive. The qualities of T700/VB-90 composite have been improved significantly by incorporating air release additive BYK®-A 560. Mechanical properties and hot/wet tests have proved that there is no negative influence of BYK®-A 560 on the main mechanical properties and heat resistance of T700/VB-90 composite which can be serviced as high as 90°C as a structure material. The laminates manufactured from BYK®-A 560 incorporated T700/VB-90 prepreg by using vacuum bag cure only technique have excellent mechanical properties with autoclave cure quality to meet aerospace application requirements.

Acknowledgement

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